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Methodology for evaluating the fire performance of multilayer modular façades – Case study integrating solar technologies

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ABSTRACT

The evolution of the construction sector towards industrialization is driving the adoption of lightweight, prefabricated multilayer modular and preassembled envelope systems. This offers advantages in quality, execution speed and technology integration. However, their fire performance remains a critical challenge. While the Single Burning Item (SBI) test is commonly used to assess fire reaction, it often fails to capture the actual fire behaviour of complex façades.

This study introduces a novel methodology for evaluating fire performance that goes beyond standard testing requirements to meet more stringent safety criteria. The approach identifies critical areas in heterogeneous façades where fire propagation is difficult to predict. Then it was applied to a 2.2 m × 3 m façade module incorporating photovoltaic (PV), solar thermal (ST), and hybrid PVT technologies. Intermediate-scale testing was developed as a modified version of ISO 13785-1, featuring increased burner output (from 100 kW to 300 kW), altered specimen configuration (from two-wing to single-wall), and the establishment of evaluation criteria.

Two experimental tests were conducted. The first failed to meet any criteria, while the second, with design improvements and passive fire protection, met all but one (burning falling parts). The findings emphasize the importance of early-stage fire performance assessment and iterative design refinement. They also reveal that a favourable fire reaction classification does not necessarily ensure acceptable fire spread behaviour, highlighting the need for more realistic testing methods.

Intermediate-scale testing is proposed as a valid, cost-effective tool for fire performance evaluation. Future research should deepen correlations with full-scale tests and explore calorimetric analysis and cost-benefit assessments of fire protection strategies.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Industrialised construction has emerged as a transformative approach in the European building sector. This offers innovative

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solutions to address critical challenges faced by the industry while simultaneously advancing in sustainability, efficiency, and productivity. This manufacturing and building paradigm has gained significant interest due to its potential to enhance performance in a sector that has traditionally been slow to innovate [1]. In Europe, the construction industry is an important sector, providing 18 million direct jobs and accounting for approximately 9% of the European Union's GDP [2]. Buildings account for 36% of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions [3], approximately 50% of resource extraction, and over 30% of annual waste generation [4]. Consequently, the sector faces major challenges, including reducing environmental impact to meet the EU 2050 climate-neutrality target [5], improving energy efficiency [3,6], and addressing labour shortages exacerbated by the retirement of specialised workers [1].

Industrialised construction offers solutions to these issues by implementing off-site manufacturing, standardised components and advanced technologies [7]. The evolution of this approach in Europe has been gradual but accelerating. Estimations suggest that industrialised construction of single-family homes will increase from 1% in 2023 to 40% of new buildings by 2030 [8]. This shift towards industrialization is part of a broader movement towards Construction 4.0. This movement integrates digital technologies to create a physical-to-digital-to-physical relationship and aims to improve the construction industry's quality and productivity while addressing its negative environmental, social, and economic impacts [9].

In this context, modular and off-site prefabricated envelope systems play a key role in advancing industrialised construction, as they provide efficiency, sustainability, and quality benefits. These solutions enhance building energy performance by increasing façade thermal resistance, reducing onsite installation time by 20–50%, and lowering construction costs by up to 30% [10]. They are also particularly attractive for building renovation, given that an estimated 75% of the European building stock is energy inefficient [3] and that the deep renovation rate must rise from 0.2% to at least 2% per year to meet greenhouse-gas reduction and decarbonisation targets [11]. Not only because these are energy efficient solutions, but also because the disturbance to occupants is considerably reduced [12].

The shift towards off-site manufacturing of building envelopes enables the development of more complex systems that can reliably integrate technologies. In recent years, numerous envelope systems have emerged incorporating solar harvesting technologies. These include photovoltaic (PV), solar thermal (ST), or hybrid systems (PVT), designed to supply energy directly for building operations and generating integrated solutions such as Building Integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV). The aim is to achieve Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEB) in renovation projects and zero-energy or positive-energy buildings in new constructions [13–16].

1.2. Fire evaluation of multilayer modular façades

Such complex systems are typically resolved through lightweight and multi-layer designs that inherently incorporate combustible materials and cavities. This is detrimental to fire safety, as new fire igniting possibilities and potential paths to fire spread are created [17–19]. Although no official statistics on façade fires exist, Bonner and Rein reported that fires with external wall fire spread in tall buildings increased 7 times between 1990 and 2018 [20], with an average of 4.8 incidents per year [18]. As energy performance measures should not undermine building security [3], integrating fire safety considerations from the design stage is essential to ensure safe and sustainable façade systems.

Fire safety is one of the eight basic requirements of construction products defined in the Regulation of the European Parliament for the marketing of construction products (CPR) [21]. Initially introduced in 1989, the objective was to achieve harmonisation at European level. This defines that the construction products shall be designed, constructed, used and maintained in such a way that, in an event of fire, they meet the following requirements.

- (a) the load-bearing capacity of the construction works is maintained for a specific period of time to give occupants time to leave the building;
- (b) the rescue and emergency services' access is ensured and there are appropriate means to facilitate their work;
- (c) the initiation and spread of fire and smoke is controlled and limited;
- (d) the spread of the fire and smoke to the adjacent construction works is limited;
- (e) the safety of rescue and emergency services is taken into consideration.

Nevertheless, each EU Member State is the authority to define its own fire safety requirements. In this regard, in case of reaction to fire or fire resistance of façades, both testing methods and classification criteria are harmonised. However, requirements are defined by each Member State and usually depend on the use and height of the building. Nevertheless, there is evidence that some of the standards should be adapted to these new envelope systems, because they do not take into consideration some fire spread mechanisms as they are new to these systems. For instance, the fire could spread through the air cavity between the external cladding and the insulation in the façade system [22] or through the curtain walling solution [23]. In the case of external fire spread in buildings, most Member States have established the EN 13501-1 reaction to fire classification system [24] as the regulatory requirement for the fire performance of façade systems. In this standard it is mentioned that the Single Burning Item test (SBI) (EN 13823) [25] evaluates the potential contribution of a product to the development of a fire. This standard is not adequate to assess the fire performance of façade systems due to its unsuitable internal fire scenario (not valid for facade fire events) [26]. In addition, the standard suffers from an insufficient sample scale, inappropriate measurement parameters and observations, and an inability to account for the complexity of modern façade assemblies [19,26–28]. Some countries, recognizing the limitations of existing standards to properly address fire propagation in façade systems, are developing their own testing method and classification criteria for high-rise or relevant buildings [29,30]. Last country has been The Netherlands, which is working on guidelines for testing the fire safety of façades on intermediate and large scale [31]. Some countries, besides, have implemented bans on the use of combustible materials in façade cladding systems [32] for certain height or type of buildings. In this regard, the existing tests to measure the combustibility (or non-combustibility) such as the ISO 1716

or ISO 1182, were designed for assessing individual materials. These may not neither be adequate for these systems as the possible upward flame spread is not assessed [33,34] nor the possible failure in the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the building envelope [35].

In this context, the European Commission has undertaken two consecutive projects since 2017 aimed at defining a harmonised test method to assess the fire performance of façades [36,37]. This method could be directly applied to harmonised product standards (CEN) and European Assessment Documents (EOTA) for relevant construction products (e.g., kits), under the CPR framework. It ensures products are tested according to their intended end-use application [38]. As a result, a new assessment method has been defined, based on BS 8414 and DIN 4102-20 test methods, including an intermediate and a large fire exposure tests [37]. However, authors of that work agree that there are still some parts to be improved and clarified.

As the scale of a fire test increases, the tested sample more closely resembles end-use conditions, along with the associated fire scenario. This results in a more complex fire with a greater number of variables becoming relevant as more materials and system components are involved, adding more flammable materials and fire propagation paths together with the interactions between them [20]. But as the scale increases, costs do so: cost to run the test, cost to purchase materials included in the sample and construction cost to materialize the sample [39–41].

Within this context, the European Project ENSNARE [42] has developed a novel methodology for the intermediate-scale evaluation of the fire performance of multilayer modular façade systems (2 MF). ENSNARE aims developing an industrialised envelope mesh for building energy renovation projects that would incorporate different solar harvesting technologies as well as fast connection between the different layers that make it up [43]. As it is an innovative modular façade, there is no specific standard to assess the essential characteristics of this solution. Therefore, the assessment of the response to a fire situation is even more critical. In this regard, while the pre-design phase considered only the reaction to fire requirements of the demonstration countries, as the envelope design progressed, the decision to go beyond these regulatory requirements was made. This approach aimed not only to anticipate potential future regulatory changes but also to align with a holistic vision of sustainability, in which fire safety is regarded as a critical component [44,45]. Moreover, in the case of façade retrofitting within the existing building stock, it is currently common for the original façade to exhibit excellent fire performance. Therefore, it is unacceptable to result in a deterioration of the overall fire performance of the retrofitted façade when using innovative envelope systems.

Focusing on integrating fire safety into the design of the 2 MF system and using ENSNARE façade systems as case study, the main research question is formulated as follows.

- How can fire safety be effectively integrated into the early-stage design of multilayer modular façade systems, enhancing overall building safety while preserving the benefits of prefabrication efficiency and energy performance?

This main interrogation arises secondary research questions defined as follows.

- What reliable fire performance procedures exist for assessing flame spread in multilayer modular façade systems?
- How can these testing procedures be operationalised during the conceptual design phase?

A dual focus on method development and design iteration is employed herein. This approach has allowed us to systematically develop and refine fire safety testing protocols while simultaneously improving the design of the multilayer modular façade system.

The developed methodology is detailed in the following section 2, and then the case study applying the methodology to an industrialised solution is explained in subsequent section 3. Main results achieved are summarised in section 4, followed by the discussion and conclusion sections 5 and 6 respectively.

Fig. 1. Methodology developed to assess the fire performance of the multilayer modular façade in the design phase.

2. Methodology

Before implementing the methodological workflow shown in Fig. 1, a preliminary step (0) is required to develop the detailed design of the multilayer modular façade (2 MF). This stage defines the initial geometry, material composition, and functional configuration of the system, and establishes the baseline for the fire-performance assessment. Afterwards, the methodological process begins with two tasks running in parallel: (A) the analysis of the 2 MF system to identify critical points and to anticipate its behaviour under fire exposure, and (B) the definition of the intermediate-scale testing procedure. If the analysis in (A) reveals that certain critical points can be mitigated through design improvements, the process loops back to step (0) to update the detailed design before continuing. After steps (A) and (B) are completed, the test specimen is manufactured, and the fire test is conducted (C). If the test results are unsatisfactory, the process becomes iterative again, returning to the redesign stage (A) until a configuration attains the desired fire performance.

Focusing on the detailed design of system (A), the most critical features for the evaluation of its fire performance through testing are identified. Particular attention is given to the materials comprising the multilayer configuration and the cavities contained within the module. Additionally, the connections between modules are examined, especially the horizontal and vertical joints, which are common in modular façade systems. Furthermore, more versatile façade solutions employing alternative configurations are also considered. These configurations may combine different cladding types and their potential impact on fire performance requires detailed assessment. The potential negative effects of these critical points under fire conditions are analysed. Some of the consequences include fire spread and/or a sudden increase of fire load.

The next step is to assess the feasibility of mitigating these critical points. This is done either by introducing passive fire protection elements (PFP) or by modifying the façade system design, considering materials, geometries, and other relevant parameters. If mitigation is deemed feasible, the system is redesigned (0) and the process returns to step (A). Otherwise, the dimensions of the test sample are defined, along with the most unfavourable configuration in cases where the solution is customizable.

Regarding the intermediate-scale testing procedure definition (B), the first step involves collecting and analysing both European and international regulatory frameworks related to the evaluation of fire spread through façades or cladding elements using intermediate-scale testing. This regulatory analysis focuses primarily on the scope, test method, and evaluation criteria. Within the test method analysis, several key aspects are identified. These include the geometry and dimensions of the specimen, the evaluation parameters, and the monitoring infrastructure required, primarily sensors. The analysis also determines the placement of these sensors on the specimen. In addition, the fire load and its position within both the test bench and the sample are specified.

Based on this information and considering the specific characteristics of multilayer modular façade systems (2 MF), a new test method is established for evaluating fire spread in 2 MF systems. As a result, evaluation parameters and criteria, monitoring approach, and fire load location are defined.

The testing process for the manufactured sample, based on the outcomes of previous stages A and B, comprises three main steps: First, a detailed visual observation is conducted. During this stage, numerous qualitative aspects of the specimen's behaviour under

Fig. 2. Images of ENSNARE system and prototypes: (a) Exploded axonometric view with the components of the ENSNARE system. (b) Façade module integrating photovoltaic panels and active window. (c) Façade module configured by photovoltaic panels and registrable area.

fire exposure are documented. Although not quantifiable, they provide essential insights into the suitability of the system. This includes the overall fire development pattern, the identification of pathways that facilitate flame spread, heterogeneities in fire propagation, abrupt changes in combustion behaviour, variations in smoke appearance, and any structural failures occurring in the system components.

Second, the evaluation parameters are monitored and analysed. A network of sensors distributed throughout the specimen collects data during the test. Once the experiment concludes, these data are processed to characterise the evolution of the fire over the testing period and to assess the system's response in accordance with the predefined criteria.

Finally, the fire performance of the 2 MF system is determined. Drawing on the qualitative observations and the quantitative monitoring data, together with the evaluation criteria established, the system is classified as either performing favourably or unfavourably. A favourable outcome validates the system in terms of fire propagation. An unfavourable result requires restarting the iterative process.

2.1. System definition

The methodology proposed in this paper has been demonstrated using an innovative façade system developed within the framework of the European ENSNARE project [42,43]. The following paragraphs provide a description of this façade system, with a focus on those characteristics that are likely to have a significant impact on fire propagation.

The system is conceived as a 2 MF solution supported by an aluminium frame and composed of two independent layers—an inner and an outer layer. They are mechanically connected and with a ventilated air gap between them. Each of these layers is in turn composed of sublayers of different materials. The façade system incorporates a modular configuration and is designed to be anchored to a supporting wall (Fig. 2).

The inner layer provides structural integrity, thermal insulation, and both air and water tightness. In contrast, the outer layer integrates several innovative solar harvesting technologies and registrable areas for routing electrical and hydraulic services associated with these technologies across the façade. These registrable areas form a continuous track that enables the interconnection of technological panels and can be configured in either vertical or horizontal orientations. Therefore, the external layer of the ENSNARE system is customizable. The selection of the solar harvesting technologies depends on the specific energy requirements of each building. Each of these technologies features its own modularity. This customization of the outer layer inherently leads to the formation of joints between technological panels. Additionally, as the whole façade is also conceived as modular comprising both layers, vertical and horizontal joints are also present at the interfaces between modules. The ventilated air gap between the inner and outer layer does not have a uniform thickness due to the varying sections of the solar technologies.

This system also allows to incorporate glazed areas by integrating an active window. The latter is aligned with the insulation layer of the module (Fig. 2), ensuring a proper thermal performance.

Based on the information presented above, the following characteristics are identified as those that may negatively influence fire propagation across the façade: (i) the presence of cavities and the joints between modules and panels may act as pathways for fire spread; (ii) the integration of innovative solar technologies without certified reaction to fire classification introduces additional uncertainty; (iii) internal system heterogeneity complicates the establishment of a consistent fire response pattern; (iv) high temperatures may cause mechanical instabilities resulting from the thermal expansion of the aluminium frame.; and (v) transition elements between the façade and windows, such as lintels, can constitute weak points through which flames may penetrate into the system's air cavity.

2.2. Testing procedure definition

2.2.1. Regulatory framework analysis

The objective of the developed testing methodology was to assess the fire performance of the façade system defined previously. Most European Member States apply the EN 13501-1 (Euroclass) [24] fire performance classification system, which uses the EN 13823 Single Burning Item (SBI) [25] test results to determine the class of those construction products ranging from A2 to D. However, a larger scale fire test was desired for the evaluation of the system. This is because these small-scale fire tests are not appropriate to assess fire reaction of façade systems [19,27,28], particularly for the evaluation of fire propagation. Regarding larger scales, an intermediate-scale fire test has some advantages. It enables to perform tests quite rapidly and in a lower cost compared to a large-scale fire test [39,46], while they give much information on the performance of the façade in case of fire. This makes possible to compare different façade systems and support product development processes at a more affordable cost.

With these aspects in mind, different intermediate-scale test procedures to assess fire spread in external wall or cladding systems available in different countries or developed in previous studies were sought to validate envelope solutions.

Some of those studies are based on ISO 13785-1 [40,41,47,48], applicable to façades and claddings that are not free-standing and that are used as an addition to an existing external wall. The 100 kW burner has been noted as unsuitable for adequately testing the fire performance of certain systems like rainscreen facades, particularly when compared to larger tests [49]. This was in line with the study carried out by Slanina et al. [47], where the fire did not spread on and within the curtain wall. This heat exposes the façade to 50 kW/m², and it is mentioned that 70-80 kW/m² [40] or 100 kW/m² [50] could be more representative of post-flashover conditions. Besides, this standard procedure lacks evaluation criteria, so some studies rely on the local requirements of the Czech Republic, where it is mandated [47]. Lastly, some studies suggest that this testing procedure can be used to discriminate between solutions. This could be a powerful tool to complement any reference-scale test, for example, in the case of extended applications [41,48]. Additionally, in some of these cases, measurements of the heat release rate and other parameters have been taken, providing more comprehensive

information.

Other studies, particularly those related to insurance companies, are based on FM 4880 16-ft Parallel Panel Test [50,51], for the fire performance evaluation of cladding wall assemblies. In these cases, a higher and potentially more realistic heat flux exposure ($>100 \text{ kW/m}^2$) is used, making it more discriminant for evaluating Aluminium Composite Material assemblies [51]. However, the required specimen surface area is approximately 10 m^2 , which is substantially larger than the $4,32 \text{ m}^2$ needed for the ISO 13785-1 test. This larger sample size can be seen as a disadvantage, as it increases material consumption and complicates test logistics.

A study was conducted to assess four different rainscreen façade systems using a modified large-scale BS 8414-1 test [49]. In this case the specimen height was reduced to 5 m and the heat release rate was also measured. It was concluded that the 3 MW crib dominated the burning behaviour during the test, providing little opportunity to see differences between different samples.

Cancelliere et al. [52] developed a new mid-scale testing procedure to evaluate the fire behaviour for façades with ETICS, hitting the façade with a 300 kW linear burner and inside a room corner test (ISO 9705) equipment for gas analysis. In this case, the heat fluxes recorded during the test were in line with those measured in other large-scale tests carried out by Oleszkiewicz [53].

There are two other mid-scale test methods similar to ISO 13785-1, in the sense that similar fire scenarios are created (inside the building). The DIN 4102-20 is used in Switzerland and Germany to classify cladding systems as low flammable systems while the ÖNORM B 3800-5 is used in Switzerland and Austria [54] and is applicable to ventilated façades, non-ventilated façades and ETICS. Lastly, there is another mid-scale test, in which a fire from outside the building is represented; the PN-B-02867, used in Poland [54] and for all façade systems. In the case of the DIN 4102-20, the minimum area of the test specimen, more than 15 m^2 [55], is quite larger than the ISO 13785-1. The ÖNORM B 3800-5 test standard, creates the fuel with a 25 kg wood crib, which does not permit to simulate the entire length of the flames out of a window after a flash over, but simulates the peak of the flames [56]. The fuel load required for the PN-B-02867 is similar, which consists of a 20 kg wood crib, but located in the outside of the outer façade, and $1.75 \text{ m} \times 2.5 \text{ m}$ sample size [57]. In this sense, gas burners provide more repeatable results in the same conditions, as they can guarantee a constant flame power, unlike wood cribs [52]. Moreover, several benefits have been reported; decreased height, less cleaning, higher safety and, so therefore, less costs associated to the test [37].

After the preliminary analysis, considering the 2 MF system to be installed on an existing external wall, it was decided to assess its fire performance using the intermediate-scale test ISO 13785-1 [58] as basis. This standard was selected because it is the most frequently referenced in the scientific literature and is officially adopted in the Netherlands, ensuring both methodological consistency and regulatory relevance. However, we found it necessary to make some modifications and adaptations to the test methodology. Additionally, we developed evaluation criteria, as the original test method did not include any. These are explained in the following section.

2.2.2. Development of testing procedure and evaluation criteria

Modifications were made to ISO 13785-1, as it is less demanding than other intermediate-scale fire tests such as the DIN 4102-20 or large-scale fire tests such as the BS8414-1 [55]. These modifications were based on literature review and insights gained from previous research and experiments conducted in intermediate- and large-scale fire tests. The reason for modifying the standardised test was mainly to better reflect real-world conditions observed in larger-scale fire scenarios, but also to have a cost-effective approach. The main changes are first explained and justified and then the evaluation criteria are developed.

Main adaptations to ISO 13785-1 are summarised in Table 1. Main changes refer to the test specimen, both configuration and dimensions, and to the fire source position and exposure, which is related to the fire scenario. Special attention is given to these aspects.

Regarding test specimen configuration, one wing configuration was selected. The standard size of the basic module of the façade system was defined as $2.2 \text{ m} \times 3.0 \text{ m}$ and a total thickness ranging from 280 to 320 mm. The two-wing specimen would not fit in the bench of the ISO 13785-1, which has a dimension of 2.4 m of width. Besides, the single-wall configuration reduces cost and complexity

Table 1

Proposed main adaptations to the ISO 13785-1.

Item (Section in ISO 13785-1)	ISO 13785-1	Proposed adaptation
Scope (1)	Applicable to façades and claddings that are not free standing and that are used as an addition to an existing external wall	Applicable also to free standing façades
Environment (5.2)	Open laboratory environment	Indoor
Test specimen (7)	Two wings ($1.2 \text{ m} \times 2.4 \text{ m} + 0.6 \text{ m} \times 2.4 \text{ m}$).	One wing ($2.2 \text{ m} \times 3.0 \text{ m}$)
Fire source and exposure (6)	Burner placed on the floor lengthwise below the specimen with the ends of the burner lined up with the edges of the test specimen. Back wall of the burner in contact with the sample holder.	Burner placed on the floor lengthwise below with the test specimen and centred with the specimen vertical axis. Back wall of the burner aligned in depth with the outer face of the sample.
Thermocouples (8.1)	Propane heat output (100 ± 5) kW. Surface thermocouples positioned centrally on the external surface at the joint of the test specimen at distances of 0.5 m, 1 m, 1.5 m, 2 m, 2.4 m from the bottom edge of the test specimen. Internal thermocouples central in the air cavity, at 1.2 m and 2.3 m from the bottom edge of the test specimen	Propane heat output (300 ± 5) kW. External thermocouples positioned 10 mm outwards from the external face of the cladding at 0.5 m, 1 m, 1.5 m, 2 m, 2.5 m and 3 m from the bottom edge of the test specimen. Internal thermocouples positioned the mid-depth of each combustible layer $>10 \text{ mm}$ thick and of any air cavity, at 0.5 m, 1 m, 1.5 m, 2 m, 2.5 m and 3 m from the bottom edge of the test specimen

of mounting [50]. This has an impact on the heat flux resulted in the sample. The corner configuration is the most vulnerable, as the air entrainment is considerably reduced and so the rate of mixing with ambient air is lower. This results in a less rapidly decrease of the temperature of the buoyant plume, higher flame heights [59], and higher heat fluxes. This aspect is something to consider when defining the fire scenario and fire source position and exposure, which is defined hereafter.

The possible fire scenarios related to these types of façade systems could be the following: fire initiation in the air cavity of the system or fire initiation in its external part. The latter is the fire scenario that we wanted to create. In that case, the ignition source could be (1) in the interior of the building venting through a window or (2) in the exterior of the building due to a fire from a dumpster, vehicle, balcony, a wildland-urban-interface fire [51] or fire in an adjacent building. In the case of (1) we would be talking about post-flashover compartment heat flux exposures, where realistic heat fluxes have been defined as values between 70 and 100 kW/m² for single wall specimens [40]. In the case of (2) we would be talking about exterior fires with an exposure to the walls of 110 kW/m².

The peak heat fluxes on the façade of the different large-scale façade fire tests are between 40 kW/m² and 110 kW/m² [51,60]. In the case of the ISO 13785-1, heat flux is 50 kW/m² [40,60], typifying an external fire with flames impinging directly upon a façade. We wanted to simulate a more realistic scenario closer to the 100 kW/m², which would happen due to an external fire scenario with flames impinging directly upon a façade. Considering the single-wall specimen configuration and the above-mentioned aspects, we defined a fire source consisting of a propane burner with a heat output of 300 kW. This was in line with what Cancelliere et al. defined [52] and the power of the ignition source defined in the ISO 9705, where a burner of 1.250 m length is used.

Another important consideration at this stage is the position of the burner. According to ISO 13785-1, back wall of the burner shall be in contact with the sample holder, being the size of the burner 1.2 m × 0.1 m × 0.15 m (length × width × depth). Nevertheless, in cases where thick cladding systems are assessed, energy output of the fire source could be lost to the surroundings and the underside of the façade before flames reaching the front side of the specimen [61]. In this particular case of ENSNARE system, with a 320 mm thickness, we decided that the back wall of the burner should be aligned in depth with the outer face of the sample. This way the fire scenario created would still be an external fire that reaches the façade. This is also an aspect that should have been considered if a combustion chamber was selected instead of the linear burner as defined in ISO 13785-1. For thick samples an external fire scenario would probably be more severe than a post flash-over compartment fire, which would have been simulated with a fire source through a combustion chamber and a window.

Based on these considerations and insights from previous research and experiments, a heat output of 300 kW was selected, and a single-wall configuration was used. To validate this decision and to better understand the fire scenario that would be created, a series of preliminary tests were conducted using a non-combustible material (silicate boards). We compared the conditions achieved with a 100-kW heat source and two wings, versus a 300-kW heat source and a single wall. The average temperature and heat flux values measured during these tests are provided in [Supplementary Fig. S5](#). With the proposed changes in specimen configuration and heat output, the fire scenario would more closely resemble those observed in large-scale fires. At a height of 610 mm above the bottom of the specimen (corresponding to 860 mm above the top of the burner), a heat flux of 47 kW/m² could be achieved.

Regarding environment, it is decided that the test is performed indoors to enhance repeatability [61,62]. Besides, this would enable to perform the test under a large-scale calorimetric hood and measure the gases released during the test.

As previously mentioned, ISO 13785-1 has no evaluation criteria defined. Moreover, the criteria are still under development in Europe, resulting in significant variation among member countries. Hence, based mainly on the NFPA 285 [63] large-scale fire test method and the BR135 [64] guideline, some evaluation criteria were developed. The NFPA 285 offers greater practical experience and a more stable regulatory framework, while the BR135 serves as the foundation for the evaluation criteria within the new European approach, thus maintaining a balance between established knowledge and emerging European trends. Below the evaluation criteria are detailed.

The test specimen shall be considered as passing the fire test when the following performance criteria are met during the 30-min test duration (as defined in NFPA 285 [63] and considering that end of test according to ISO 13785-1 is when the upper edge of the test specimen is extensively flaming or after 30 min).

Criterion A: Flame propagation: Exterior face of test specimen.

Flame propagation on the exterior face of the test specimen shall not occur vertically beyond the upper limit of the test specimen (as defined in NFPA 285 [63]), provided that the flame propagation is sustained for at least 10 s [65]. The 10-s threshold is introduced to avoid subjective interpretation of transient or intermittent flame events, in line with the update of Draft International Standard ISO/DIS 13785-1:2025. In the NFPA Standard horizontal flame propagation is also defined, but we did not include this criterion because this phenomenon would not be easy to check considering both sample's and burner's width.

Criterion B: Flame propagation: Internal layers of test specimen.

Flame propagation shall not occur vertically beyond the upper limit of the test specimen through the combustible components and/or air cavities within the test specimen.

Criterion C: External temperatures.

External temperatures at 10 mm from the external face of the specimen shall not exceed 500 °C + ambient temperature and remain above this value for at least 30 s as measured by thermocouples installed at a height of 3000 mm from the lower edge of the sample.

The external temperature threshold is set at 500 °C above ambient temperature. This relative-to-ambient approach aligns with BS 8414 and the new European fire tests for façades [37], accounting for varying ambient conditions at different testing locations. Thermocouples were installed at a height of 3000 mm from the lower edge of the specimen, corresponding to 3250 mm above the burner. This height is comparable to the 3050 mm reference point in NFPA 285 (measured from the top of the window opening). The criterion is met when the temperature exceeds the threshold for at least 30 s, as defined in the new European fire tests for façades and the BR135 [64].

Criterion D: Internal temperatures.

Internal temperatures in the mid-depth of each combustible layer >10 mm thick and of any air cavity shall not exceed 500 °C + ambient temperature, as measured by thermocouples installed at 3000 mm from the lintel.

This was defined based in NFPA 285 and BR135 [66]. According to NFPA 285 a temperature of 538 °C at a height of 3019 mm above the top of the window opening, whereas in BR135 a temperature of 600 °C for a period of at least 30 s at a height of 5000 mm.

Criterion E: Burning falling parts.

Burning parts fallen from the façade system, either in liquid or solid phase, shall not burn for 30 s or longer after hitting the ground. Requirement addressing falling parts and burning debris or droplets was included, although it is not included in NFPA 285, as these could pose significant risks to evacuation efforts, rescue personnel, and fire brigades. This aspect is required in some European countries, although with varying definitions and implementation standards [36].

The performance of the test specimen shall be determined on the basis of visual observations, both during and after the test, in conjunction with the temperature data obtained during the fire test (as defined in NFPA 285 [63]). Visual observations shall be supported by continuous video recordings of the exposed face, covering the full height and width of the specimen.

3. Case study: façade system evaluation & redesign

The regulation applicable in the three demonstration buildings of the project required, at a minimum, the assessment of the façade solution in accordance with EN 13501-1. Therefore, prior to initiating the analysis of the system's behaviour in relation to fire propagation, the corresponding SBI tests were conducted.

Table 2 summarises the test results obtained for each sample, based on one individual SBI test. Each specimen differed solely in the composition of its external layer, which incorporated a distinct solar technology: (i) a photovoltaic panel laminated on an aluminium substrate (PV-Al), (ii) a photovoltaic panel laminated on a synthetic stone substrate (PV-SS), (iii) a solar thermal panel (ST), (iv) a hybrid panel —thermal and photovoltaic— (PVT) and (v) a high-pressure laminate panel (HPL) with enhanced flame retardant properties corresponding to the cladding of the registrable areas.

The following sections describe the process followed with case study and with the application of the testing procedure.

3.1. Initial design

As outlined in the methodology (Fig. 1), the first step is to identify the critical points potentially facilitating fire propagation along the façade. Based on this information, the next step is to define the geometry and configuration of the test specimen.

The following potential weaknesses were identified: (1) cavities and joints, (2) reaction to fire of the components and façade system, (3) different configurations of the system, (4) fire behaviour of the frame, (5) lintel.

The façade system incorporates various types of cavities (1) enabling a more effective fire spread. One of them is the registrable area that interconnects modules along the entire infrastructure layout. The cladding of these areas is solved by means of HPL panels. It is reasonable to assume that the vertical registrable area may promote a chimney effect in the event of a fire.

The main joints between modules are tongue-and-groove in the inner layer and open in the outer layer of the system. The secondary joints between the technologies located in the outer layer are open joints and they can be horizontals and verticals. The number of secondary joints in each module depends on the number of technological panels included.

Finally, the air cavity between the inner and the outer layer does not maintain a uniform thickness across the system due to the

Table 2

The expected reaction to fire classification (EN 13501-1) based on one individual SBI test performed to each of the panels.

Sample (type of cladding)	Expected reaction to fire classification
(i) Photovoltaic technology with aluminium substrate – PV-Al	B-s1,d0*
(ii) Photovoltaic technology with synthetic stone substrate – PV-SS	B-s1,d0*
(iii) Solar Thermal technology – ST	B-s1,d0*
(iv) Hybrid technology – PVT	B-s1,d0*
(v) High pressure laminate panel – HPL	B-s1,d0*

B = very limited contribution to fire; s1 = low smoke emission quantity and speed; d0 = no flaming droplets or particles.

customised outer layer configuration. This heterogeneity may lead to abrupt changes in fire development.

The reaction to fire classification of the components and the whole system (2) is aimed at identifying and addressing potential weaknesses within the system. It focuses especially on components with poor classifications, as these could negatively influence the outcome of the intermediate-scale test.

Given the customisability of the outer layer of the façade system (3), different combinations may result in different responses to a fire spreading situation. Regarding material composition, the ST and PVT technologies include a layer of stone wool on their rear face, which acts as a protective barrier when exposed to fire. In contrast, the rear face of the PV technologies —PV-Al and PV-SS— is in direct contact with the air cavity and therefore lacks such protection. Moreover, considering the different substrates of PV-Al panel —aluminium— and PV-SS —synthetic stone— the last one is expected to perform better against fire than PV-Al.

In addition, the ENSNARE system is based on an aluminium frame (4) composed of bar-type elements. Specific design rules apply to such systems to prevent deformation incompatibilities caused by temperature changes in elements exposed to outdoor conditions. However, in exceptional situations such as a fire, temperatures may far exceed the admissible range for which the system was designed, potentially leading to structural instability issues.

Finally, the intermediate-scale fire test places the fire source at the bottom of the specimen, where transition elements in real installations are often resolved using metallic framing components. When analysing the suitability of these materials, it is important to note that aluminium undergoes plastic deformation at lower temperatures than steel and has a significantly lower melting point. It also experiences greater thermal expansion due to its higher thermal-expansion coefficient. Therefore, aluminium is considerably more thermally unstable than steel. The lower lintel of the specimen (5) to be tested is the element most exposed to fire and acts as the first barrier against fire propagation.

Table 3 summarises the critical points identified in the ENSNARE façade system. This table includes their characteristics, their potential influence in the event of a fire, and the measures and considerations adopted for defining the test specimen.

Considering the information gathered in the previous analysis, the initial strategy for defining the configuration of the test sample was to identify the worst-case scenario.

The test sample must contain a vertical registrable area. Given the high likelihood of a chimney effect occurring in this element, one stone wool barrier was installed along the registrable area, covering its entire cross-section. In this specimen, the hydraulic circuit pipes and electrical wiring were not included.

The sample must include at least one horizontal joint and one vertical joint representing the connection between different modules. This is intended to analyse whether these can facilitate the spread of fire between modules.

The specimen is designed to incorporate all solar technologies developed within the project in its outer layer. Although the demonstrator buildings combined two or three technologies per module, their façades invariably included transition zones where different module typologies converged. Due to the highest heterogeneity, these areas represent the configuration with the greatest uncertainty in terms of fire behaviour. For this reason, the test specimen is configured to reproduce this worst-case scenario by concentrating the four technologies within a single assembly. To further represent the most adverse fire exposure conditions, the PV based technologies are positioned in the lower part of the specimen, where they are directly exposed to the ignition source. In contrast, the upper section included ST and PVT technologies. This configuration enables the evaluation of several aspects: (1) the fire behaviour at the secondary joints formed between different technological panels; (2) the extent of fire impact on the different technologies; and (3) the development of fire along the air cavity.

Finally, the lower lintel was materialised using a folded steel sheet. This decision was based on the observation that the ignition source directly affects this element, making enhanced fire performance a critical requirement.

Based on these guidelines, the design of the test sample was defined. Four modules configure the sample. Table 4 includes

Table 3

Critical aspects detected in the ENSNARE façade system and considerations to define the test sample.

Critical points	Characteristics	Fire behaviour consequence/ evaluation ^a	Consideration for test sample definition	Fire protection measure	
Cavities	Registrable Areas (RA)	(95 × 300-450) mm	Fire spread/Relevant in vertical position	Vertical RA need to be evaluated	Stone wool barrier in vertical RA
	Main joints	(25-85 × 230) mm	Fire spread/not prioritised	A vertical & horizontal main joint need to be evaluated	-
	Secondary joints	(25-45 × 100) mm	Fire spread/not prioritised	Need to be evaluated	-
Reaction to fire of the cladding panels	Ventilated air gap	15-95 mm	Fire spread & uncertainty about fire development pattern/not prioritised	Greater air gap thickness at the bottom of the sample ^b	-
	Customizable outer layer	> B-s1, d0	Contribution to fire/not prioritised	Include all the technologies	-
Aluminium frame	ST&PVT protected in rear side PV techn. not protected in rear side	No fire response pattern/not prioritised	PV techn. In the bottom area of the sample ^b	-	
Lintel	Aluminium alloy EN AW 6063 Metal plate	Instability of the system/not prioritised	-	-	
		Fire spread/Aluminium vs steel	-	Steel plate	

^a Evaluation of the need to include some fire protection measures.

^b These considerations must be compatible.

information regarding each module and Fig. 3 shows the mock-up of the specimen. The specimen was prepared and assembled by the manufacturer as a complete assembly, ensuring consistent end-conditions.

Temperature was recorded with Type-K thermocouples (1.5 mm diameter, mineral insulated sheath) at a 10 s acquisition interval. Those were distributed across the sample as illustrated in Fig. 4. External sensors were positioned 10 mm from the outer face of each panel to monitor surface temperatures. Internal thermocouples were placed at various depths within the profiles and cavities to capture temperature gradients. Specifically, sensors were installed at the mid-depth of the profile in both the external and internal cavities, as well as at the mid-depth after the weatherproofing vapour barrier membrane and within the external cavity. This arrangement ensures comprehensive monitoring of thermal behaviour throughout the different components and layers of the test sample, enabling accurate assessment of heat transfer and temperature distribution under experimental conditions.

3.2. Test 1

During Test 1 visual observations and data regarding temperatures and heat flux were recorded. In this section, we focus on those critical aspects already defined for the ENSNARE façade system (summarised in Table 3) that could be improved through the redesign strategy. Events are expressed in minutes and seconds since the start of the test. Detailed temperature-log plots are presented in the Supplementary Materials (see Supplementary Figs. S1–S4).

Fire propagation was observed to occur first through the cavities within the joints. Starting at 4'30", discontinuous flaming was observed along both, the main and secondary vertical joints, with no clear distinction in the behaviour between the two. By 5'30", flames were observed extending upward through the joint on the right side of the RA. Shortly after, flaming began at the upper left cavity portion of the RA and the adjacent upper right section of the PVT cavity, which is located to the left of the RA. The flames at the RA remained visible for approximately 10 s, while those on the PVT continued until 7'14". These observations indicate that the cavity system, whether associated with the joints or potentially behind the panels, played a significant role in enabling fire propagation. The behaviour of both the main and secondary joints was similar in this regard, suggesting that they can be considered functionally analogous in terms of fire spread.

Besides, criterion about internal temperatures (the ones located in the air cavity of the upper part of the specimen) not reaching 500 °C above the ambient temperature was not met for any of the thermocouples positioned to analyse that criteria (Fig. 5): for thermocouple T35 in the mid-depth of the cavity of the registrable area in 23'20", and for thermocouples T28 and T29 located in the main vertical joint (the one on the left of the RA) in 28'10" (see Fig. 4 for the positioning of thermocouples).

Regarding the horizontal joints, flames were first observed emerging from the joint between the PV-Al and PVT at 9'57", leading to the ignition of the upper sections, particularly the gasket located between the frame of the PVT panel and its technological part. This was likely the first visible exit point of the flames, as the vertical cavity narrowed at this location, causing a flame ejection through the horizontal joint. Similarly, the horizontal joint between the PV-SS and ST showed a flame emergence since section also narrowed at this location. This happened at a later stage (13'), probably because both the panel was farther from the burner, and flames entered in the interlayer used in the lamination of the PV-SS, so combustible depletion was retarded. In contrast, the horizontal joint within the RA did not exhibit early flame emergence. Instead, the upper HPL panel of the RA began to burn because of direct exposure to the flames from the cavity, rather than through the joint itself.

As for the fire behaviour of the cladding panels, each panel showed different combustion behaviours. In the case of the PV-Al panel, the glass broke early, allowing the interlayer to ignite and initiate combustion. The HPL panel, on the other hand, showed a more gradual progression of combustion across both its outer and inner surfaces. As for the PV-SS panel, it was observed that first the gaskets were burnt, so that the panel was detached from the frame. Then the encapsulants used in the lamination of the PV with the synthetic stone panel behind ignited and burned, solar cells sliding downward within the interlayer. Finally, the photovoltaic panel and the synthetic stone collapsed at 23'19".

Regarding the panels located in the upper part of the specimen, they also presented different fire behaviours. Both the PVT and ST panels demonstrated superior fire performance compared to the PV and HPL panels. For the ST panel, flames were observed emerging from the lower horizontal joint; however, this module did not exhibit significant overall damage. Meanwhile, flames were primarily concentrated around the PVT and HPL panels. The PVT initially ignited at the gasket joint between the panel and its frame, followed by cracking and the combustion of the interlayer. At 25'09", the panel released multiple glass fragments. Despite this, the upper part remained largely undamaged, and no visible flame propagation was observed on the cladding surface, although propagation did occur within the cavity. In contrast, the HPL panel displayed a gradual upward burning progression, with flames advancing until they reached the cavity barrier, which temporarily restricted further vertical flame and heat propagation. However, after approximately 21 min from the start of the test, the flames bypassed the cavity barrier through the gasket joint between the frame and the HPL panel

Table 4
Configuration of test sample 1.

Module	Panel	Position within the sample	Dimensions (mm × mm)
Module (A)	PVT	Top left	1130 × 1820
Module (B)	RA + ST	Top right	1070 × 1820
Module (C)	PV-Al	Bottom left	1130 × 1180
Module (D)	RA + PV-SS	Bottom right	1070 × 1180
Overall dimensions of the sample			2200 × 3000

Fig. 3. Left. Design of the specimen for Test 1. Right. Test sample.

Fig. 4. Positioning of the thermocouples and heat flux meter in sample 1, with dimensions in millimetres.

frame. This led to sustained combustion in the upper part of the cladding, failing criterion about flame propagation on the exterior face of the cladding (Fig. 6). This highlights both the initial effectiveness and the eventual limitations of the cavity barrier system.

As for the fire behaviour of the framing material, the decision to use a steel lintel instead of aluminium has shown to effectively enhance fire performance of the frame. Although early distortion of the steel lintel was observed at 1'47", it remained structurally intact throughout the duration of the test. In contrast, an aluminium lintel would have melted at an earlier stage, as evidenced by the melting of the lower part of the aluminium frame observed during the test.

Sample was totally damaged by the end of the test, as can be seen in Fig. 7.

The results of Test 1 are summarised in Table 5. None of the evaluation criteria were met. Summarised, the first criterion to fail was the continuous flame above the upper limit at minute 5, followed by burning falling parts at minute 13, with all the remaining criteria failing after minute 23.

Fig. 5. Internal thermocouples at 3000 mm height from lintel measured in Test 1, with the limit defined for that criterion (D).

Fig. 6. External thermocouples at 3000 mm height from lintel measured in Test 1, with the limit defined for that criterion (C). Numbered from left to right.

Fig. 7. Sample during (12:50) and after test 1.

3.3. Redesign strategy

The intermediate-scale fire test provided valuable insights into the performance of the 2 MF façade on fire propagation. While some of these observations were anticipated in our initial hypotheses, the experimental findings have confirmed them.

The criticality of the vertical Registrable Area (1) was clearly demonstrated. The cavity barrier installed in it delayed the fire propagation to the upper part of the RA, however, it could not do it during the whole test.

The effectiveness and limitations of the cavity barrier (2) was evaluated by analysing the temperature profiles recorded by thermocouples in the RA. Specifically, T32 and T33 (positioned below the barrier) and T34 and T35 (positioned above the barrier) showed significant differences in temperature trends. Hence, it was possible to demonstrate that the barrier effectively limited both heat transfer and flame propagation to the upper sections until 21' of the test (see [Supplementary Figure S1 \(a\)](#)). After this period, although the cavity barrier remained intact, flames were able to spread to the upper part of the cavity and inner side of the panel, via the joint of the cladding panel and the frame. The interaction between panel pyrolysis and the continuous supply of oxygen within the air cavity promoted vertical flame propagation. Consequently, a noticeable increase in temperature was observed in the thermocouples located above the cavity barrier, demonstrating the barrier ineffectiveness in such circumstances.

Moreover, the test revealed that main and secondary joints between different modules and technological panels served as critical pathways for vertical flame propagation and heat transfer (3). This finding suggests the need to study the installation of intumescent bands at these locations to further delay fire spread.

Because the 2 MF system is configured with different materials, distinct thermal and mechanical responses were observed during the test (4). The aluminium frames, in particular the bottom profiles and the vertical profiles within the RA, experienced significant thermal degradation under fire exposure, indicating notable heat transfer through these components (4a). The glass panes also exhibited differentiated behaviour (4b). The PV-Al and PVT panels developed cracking and released small, detached glass particles. This effect was more pronounced in the PV-Al panel, which was positioned closer to the burner. In contrast, the PV-SS panel did not crack. Once the gasket failed, the entire PV-SS glass pane detached and fell as a single piece. The steel lintel remained largely intact at the end of the test, demonstrating considerable thermal resilience, although it may have contributed to heat conduction toward the aluminium profiles positioned above it (4c). The technological panels showed clearly distinct fire behaviours (4d). Among all systems, the ST panel exhibited the most favourable fire behaviour, not only due to its greater distance from the fire source but also owing to its intrinsic material properties, as it contains no combustible interlayers. In contrast, the PV and PVT panels incorporate combustible interlayer materials within their glass panes. Flames were able to penetrate the interlayer, compromising the panel's integrity and sustaining combustion. Finally, the test also documented the occurrence of falling parts (5), which poses additional hazards during façade fires.

These findings provided a solid foundation for the redesign strategy to improve the fire-performance of the façade systems. A generalised intervention in the system strategy was adopted. New passive fire protection elements (PFP) were implemented in critical areas where fire spread accelerated, ultimately leading to failure in the control parameters. In addition, another configuration of the outer layer was considered. This redesign didn't involve modifications to the cladding panel materials, as this could imply changes in other performance aspects of the developed panels. To facilitate a clearer understanding of how the redesign strategy was addressed, [Table 6](#) summarises the findings from Test 1 alongside the protective measures implemented in Sample 1 and the additional design modifications introduced in Sample 2 to enhance its behaviour in Test 2.

Based on the previous analysis, Sample 2 was configured with a set of targeted design modifications and mitigation measures.

Given that the behaviour of both main and secondary joints was analogous in the first test, it was decided to manufacture a sample for the second test that just represented a single module unit. This configuration included only secondary joints between the panels of the outer layer. The use of a single module enabled a more detailed analysis of the fire behaviour within the basic unit of the façade system, which may integrate different technologies. Moreover, the presence of both vertical and horizontal secondary joints, all treated with PFP elements, provided relevant information to identify the measures that may need to be implemented in the main joints

Table 5
Results of the evaluation criteria in Test 1.

Evaluation criteria	Test 1 results	Minute: Seconds	PASS/ FAIL
A) Flame propagation on the exterior face of the test specimen shall not occur vertically beyond the upper limit of the test specimen.	Flames on the exterior face of the RA reached vertically beyond the upper limit	27:33	FAIL
B) Flame propagation shall not occur vertically beyond the upper limit of the test specimen through the combustible components and/or air cavities within the test specimen.	Flames in the internal layers of the PVT and air cavity of RA reached vertically beyond the upper limit	5:30	FAIL
C) External temperatures at 10 mm from the external face of the specimen shall not exceed $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} + \text{ambient temperature}$ and remain above this value for at least 30 s, as measured by thermocouples installed at a height of 3000 mm from the lintel.	2 thermocouples registered temperatures exceeded $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ limit for at least 30 s	T10; 28:20 T14; 28:40	FAIL
D) Internal temperatures in the mid-depth of each combustible layer >10 mm thick and of any air cavity shall not exceed $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} + \text{ambient temperature}$, as measured by thermocouples installed at 3000 mm from the lintel.	3 thermocouples registered temperatures exceeded $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ limit for at least 30 s	T35; 23:20 T28, T29; 28:10	FAIL
E) Burning parts fallen from the façade system do not burn for 30 s or longer after hitting the ground	Burning parts fallen from the façade system have been burning on the ground for >30 s	12:52	FAIL

Table 6

Measures introduced in Sample 2 based on Test 1 findings and comparison with Sample 1.

Behaviour of Sample 1 in the test to be improved	Protective measure implemented in Sample 1	Mitigation measure implemented in Sample 2
Fire propagation to the upper part from the cavity of the RA (finding (1))	1 cavity barrier	1 cavity barrier above each horizontal joint
Fire propagation and heat transfer via joints and cladding panel of the RA (finding (2))	No measure applied	Add a horizontal joint to the cladding panel to create a discontinuity
Flame propagation and heat transfer via joints (finding (3))	No measure applied	Intumescent bands at joint intersections
Thermal degradation and heat transfer of aluminium frames (finding (4a))	No measure applied	Horizontal cavity barrier in the base of the sample. Vertical stone wool strips attached to the vertical aluminium profiles of the RA & intumescent band along the joint between vertical aluminium profile of the cladding panel and the main frame
Cracking of glass panes (finding (4b))	No measure applied	Redistribution of technologies configuration Do not place PV-Al technology above the lintel
Steel lintel performance (finding (4c))	No measure applied	Horizontal cavity barrier above it
Different fire behaviour of the panels (finding (4d))	No measure applied	Redistribution of technologies configuration & passive protection measures introduced previously
Falling parts (finding (5))	No measure applied	Passive protection measures introduced previously to retard the fire spread and heat transfer, via cavity barriers & intumescent strips.

between adjacent modules, if required.

The outer layer is composed of three horizontal levels of solar technologies. [Table 7](#) and [Fig. 8](#) show the configuration of the specimen for Test 2. In contrast to Sample 1, this configuration was selected to deliberately create a discontinuity in the cladding of the vertical RA. As in Sample 1, this vertical area is positioned at the centre of the specimen and extends along its full height. The photovoltaic technology PV-SS remained at the base of the specimen. In addition, an additional horizontal cavity was introduced at this level, in the right side of the sample, to represent a section of a horizontal registrable area. This configuration was replicated in the upper part of the sample, in this case using PV-Al technology. Both horizontal registrable areas are connected to the vertical one. This configuration reproduces the intersections commonly required in real installations where the solar technology infrastructure runs across multiple floors before reaching the access point to the building. Importantly, the inclusion of horizontal registrable areas intersecting the vertical one enables the assessment of potential bidirectional flame-spread pathways within the façade system. At the intermediate level of the sample, PVT and ST technologies were installed. This configuration of the system's outer layer resulted in a variable air cavity thickness behind the solar technologies.

In addition, the integration of PFP elements into Sample 2 was evaluated based on the findings of Test 1 and the measures listed in [Table 6](#). [Table 8](#) and [Fig. 9](#) present the description and location of the implemented PFP elements to reduce heat transfer and to block flame propagation along the specimen.

Thermocouples were distributed across the sample following the same logics as explained for sample 1. Thermocouples in sample of Test 2 are illustrated in [Fig. 10](#).

3.4. Test 2

In this section we focus on the observations and measurements related to the most critical aspects as defined in [Table 3](#), analysing the impact of the measures adopted in the redesign strategy ([Table 8](#)). Detailed temperature-log plots are presented in the Supplementary Materials (see [Supplementary Figs. S1–S4](#)).

Little to no fire propagation through the vertical cavities in the profiles was observed during Test 2, indicating that the intumescent strips performed as intended along the test duration. However, in the 26'13", a limited amount of sustained flaming was observed through the vertical profiles at the right of the lower part of the RA.

Regarding the cavity behind the panels, a detailed analysis of the temperature evolution was carried out focusing on the vertical

Table 7

Configuration of test sample 2.

Module	Panel	Position within the sample	Dimensions (mm × mm)
Module (A)	PV-Al	Upper level – left	1130 × 595
	RA	Upper level – middle	475 × 595
	RA	Upper level – right	595 × 595
	PVT	Intermediate level – left	1130 × 1820
	RA	Intermediate level - middle	475 × 1820
	ST	Intermediate level – right	595 × 1820
	PV-SS	Bottom level – left	1130 × 585
	RA	Bottom level - middle	475 × 585
	RA	Bottom level - right	595 × 585
	Overall dimensions of the sample		

Fig. 8. Left. Design of the specimen for Test 2. Right. Test sample.

Table 8
Passive fire protection elements included in sample of Test 2.

Component	Use in the façade system	Material description	Parameters
Intumescent strip (1)	Strip to close the lateral joints in the vertical RA	Intumescent material	Width: 20 mm Thickness: 2 mm
Intumescent strip (2)	Strip to close the secondary joints in the intersections of technological panels	Intumescent material	Width: 50 mm Thickness: 1.5 mm
Gasket	Sealant for intumescent strips (2)	Gasket	Colour: Transparent Density: 1.15 g/cm ³
Cavity barrier (1)	Horizontal barriers to close the air cavity between the outer and the inner layer of the system. Located at the bottom of the sample and in the vertical RA	Stone wool and intumescent material. Open State Cassette	Width: 75 mm Depth: 100 mm
Cavity barrier (2)	Vertical barriers to protect the lateral aluminium profiles in the vertical RA	Stone wool with adhesive tape	Length: 3000 mm Width: 640-275 mm Depth: 245-300 mm

cavity in the RA, as this element was the one that most rapidly reached failure thresholds in the previous test. The internal thermocouples located in the vertical RA (Supplementary Figure S1 (b)) reveals three main phases: (1) 0–600 s (10 min), (2) 600–1100 s (18,33 min), and (3) 1100–1800 s (30 min). At the beginning of the test, the temperature rise is gradual, with higher values recorded by T33 and T37, which are positioned at the upper part of the two lowest HPL panels (0.5 and 2.3 m height from the base, respectively). In the second phase, a sudden increase in temperature is observed in the lower part of the vertical RA, caused by the detachment of the lowest HPL panel from the substructure and its combustion. Simultaneously, the thermocouples T35 and T36 located in the second HPL panel above the second cavity barrier counting from the bottom (0.8 and 1.5 m height from the base, respectively) show a moderate temperature rise that continues into the third phase. This behaviour is associated with the combustion and degradation of the HPL panel, which progressively ignites from the bottom upward during phase 2 and is fully consumed by the end of the test. Meanwhile, T39 and T40 positioned above the third cavity barrier, above 2.55 m, show only a gradual temperature increase throughout the exposure period, remaining below the threshold. This behaviour is consistent with the absence of significant damage observed in that area, aside from superficial charring and slight delamination of the HPL panel.

As a result, criteria related to the internal and external temperatures measured at 3000 mm from the lintel were met (Figs. 11 and 12, respectively) (see Fig. 13).

Regarding the fire behaviour of the different cladding panels, main observations are given below.

During the initial phase of the test, cracking sounds from the panels were predominantly heard, accompanied by the falling of small, non-flaming fragments from the panels in the lower part. Smoke was observed emerging from the upper limit above the specimen at 4'42". Around minute 7, flames were first seen at the edge between the PV-SS panel and its frame. At 7'36", flames began to emerge from the internal air cavity to the external face of the specimen, specifically at the intersection between PV-SS, PVT, and the two HPL

Fig. 9. Location of the PFP elements in sample 2. Left: Front view. Right: Cross-section. Simplified profile sections represented.

Fig. 10. Positioning of the thermocouples and heat flux meter in sample 2, with dimensions in millimetres.

panels. The HPL panel partially detached at 12'19", falling completely between minutes 17 and 18.

During the fire test, both HPL panels of the lower part of the specimen were completely consumed by the end of the exposure. In contrast, in the PV-SS panel, the portion directly above the burner was fell. The left part showed surface blackening but remained in

Fig. 11. Internal thermocouples at 3000 mm height from lintel measured in Test 2, with the limit defined for that criterion (D).

Fig. 12. External thermocouples at 3000 mm height from lintel measured in Test 2, with the limit defined for that criterion (C). Numbered from left to right.

place. Although the glass layer fractured, the encapsulant or adhesive retained the glass fragments, preventing detachment or complete disintegration.

In the second row of panels, combustion in the PVT initiated at the joint between the panel and the frame at approximately minute 8. Subsequently, the interlayer started to burn through fractures in the protective glass. The HPL panel began to combust at the joint, with the combustion progressively moving upwards, causing particles to fall —first unburned, then burning— which ultimately led to test failure at 17'59". For the ST panel, combustion started at the lower and left joints, followed by gradual fracturing and falling of the external layer.

Finally, the fire did not propagate to the cladding at the third row. These panels exhibited surface charring and in the case of the HPL slight delamination as well, attributable to exposure to elevated temperatures, but did not present any significant further damage. However, by the end of the test, sustained flaming was observed within the vertical cavity, though it did not reach the uppermost edge of the tested system. This flame was switched off by minute 40.

One evaluation criterion was not met, as burning parts of the specimen were fallen on the ground and kept burning on the ground for more than 30 s. The rest of criteria were met. These results are summarised in Table 9.

4. Results

4.1. Results of the developed testing procedure and evaluation criteria

The method developed provides a more representative scenario compared to procedures currently used in some countries. One of these procedures is the SBI (Single Burning Item) test, where a burning wastepaper basket is simulated., However, this scenario is less

Fig. 13. Sample during (02:25) and after test 2.

Table 9

Results of the evaluation criteria in Test 2.

Evaluation criteria	Test 2 results	Minute: Seconds	PASS/ FAIL
A) Flame propagation on the exterior face of the test specimen shall not occur vertically beyond the upper limit of the test specimen.	Flames on the exterior face did not reach vertically beyond the upper limit	-	PASS
B) Flame propagation shall not occur vertically beyond the upper limit of the test specimen through the combustible components and/or air cavities within the test specimen.	Flames in the internal layers did not reach vertically beyond the upper limit	-	PASS
C) External temperatures at 10 mm from the external face of the specimen shall not exceed 500 °C + ambient temperature and remain above this value for at least 30 s, as measured by thermocouples installed at a height of 3000 mm from the lintel.	External thermocouples at a height of 3000 mm from the lintel did not register temperatures that exceeded 500 °C limit for at least 30 s	-	PASS
D) Internal temperatures in the mid-depth of each combustible layer >10 mm thick and of any air cavity shall not exceed 500 °C + ambient temperature, as measured by thermocouples installed at 3000 mm from the lintel.	Internal thermocouples at 3000 mm from the lintel did not register temperatures that exceeded 500 °C limit for at least 30 s	-	PASS
E) Burning parts fallen from the façade system do not burn for 30 s or longer after hitting the ground	Burning parts fallen from the façade system have been burning on the ground for >30 s	17:59	FAIL

realistic compared to external fire exposure conditions. In the case study used to validate the methodology, it was shown that although all technologies achieved B-s1,d0 classification (Table 2), which is acceptable in some regulations, their behaviour changes completely when scaled up. This is mainly due to fire propagation effects and interactions between multiple materials. Besides, the method also allows to properly assess flame spread.

The development of this method was based on intermediate-scale testing principles described in ISO 13785-1. However, key adaptations were made to accommodate the specific characteristics of modular façade systems and to better simulate a realistic façade fire scenario, such as an increase in heat source power from 100 kW to 300 kW and the removal of the lateral wing. The procedure was therefore adapted not only for realistic fire exposure scenarios, but also for practical implementation during early façade design stages, while ensuring that the test remains representative, reproducible, and compatible with real-world façade assemblies.

4.2. Results of the fire performance of the façade system

Fire performance of the façade system was improved thanks to the redesign strategy. Test 2 met 4 out of the 5 evaluation criteria (Table 9); however, it did not satisfy the requirement that burning parts falling. In contrast, Test 1 failed to meet any of the specified criteria (Table 5).

Fire performance of the systems was notably different. In the first test, the fire had almost an unobstructed path, leading to extensive exposure of the module. In contrast, the containment achieved in the second system limited the fire attack to a more superficial level. The monitored data are presented in Supplementary Fig. S1–S4, where thermocouples were installed at the same positions in both experiments. The recorded temperatures in Test 2 are consistently lower at the thermocouples that are positioned farther from the burner. This indicates a reduced heat exposure in the more distant zones compared with Test 1 (Supplementary

Figs. S1 and S2). Analysing temperature distribution at 1500 and 2500 mm from the lintel (Supplementary Figs. S3 and S4, respectively) it is revealed that, in Test 2, the external thermocouples recorded higher temperatures whereas the internal ones recorded lower temperatures relative to Test 1. This temperature disparity is most pronounced at the larger span of 2500 mm from the lintel.

The heat flux measured on top of the specimen, was slightly higher in Test 2 compared to Test 1, as can be seen in Fig. 14. At the end of Test 1, a significant increase in heat flux was observed, coinciding with the failure of the test according to Criterion C, as the external thermocouples at 3000 mm exceeded 500 °C above ambient temperature. In Test 2, the superficial fire spread on the cladding did not propagate vertically to the upper parts of the module, likely due to the presence of three rows of panels and the interruption in panel continuity, which hindered the upward flame propagation.

When examining the fire performance of each type of panel, some similarities were observed in both tests. It should be noted that it is difficult to obtain some clear general conclusions from this case study, as different proximity to burner and sizes of the panels were used. Nevertheless, we could group all cladding elements in three types of cladding materials, based on the fire behaviour.

- PV-Al, PV-SS or PVT panels in general exhibited early glass breakage, allowing the underlying interlayer to ignite and combustion, and solar cells sliding inside could be seen. Regarding the PV-SS, it exhibited significantly different behaviours in the two tests, likely due to its different positions relative to the burner and the different sizes of the panels. In Test 1, the PV-SS was at a certain distance from the burner and was smaller. The glass pane apparently didn't break. In this case the flames accessed the interlayer of the PV and the backing substrate through the gasket, collapsing both panels at the end of the test. In Test 2, it was positioned directly above the burner and had higher dimensions. The flames impinged directly onto the sample, and a bigger thermal gradient was created not only in the panel itself, but also between the exposed and shielded areas, due to the presence of the cavity barrier. Nevertheless, just the glass and the backing substrate of the panel section located directly above the burner fell off, while the rest of the panel remained in place.
- HPL panels showed a more gradual, progressive burning affecting both the outer and inner surfaces.
- ST panels generally demonstrated the most resilient fire behaviour, limited to charring near the joints, without showing significant structural damage or spread. Nevertheless, any of the tested ST panels was located close to the burner, both were positioned in the second row of the specimen.

5. Discussion

5.1. Discussion of the developed testing procedure and evaluation criteria

In this study, an intermediate-scale test procedure to evaluate the fire performance of multilayer modular façade systems was developed. The methodology emphasizes assessing the overall system performance, rather than focusing solely on individual components, in line with the perspectives highlighted by Cernosa [40]. Such a holistic approach is essential for understanding the complex interactions and aggregate fire risks posed by façade assemblies, where the performance of the whole system may differ significantly from the sum of its parts. Main benefits of the developed testing procedure and evaluation criteria are summarised below.

The developed procedure and criteria provided valuable insights into the fire behaviour of the multilayer modular façade system and informed design improvements. While evaluation criteria not usually intended as direct regulatory requirements, this approach serves as a practical screening tool to assess fire performance at a realistic scale and guide the need for large-scale testing. This scale offers a practical balance between small-scale tests such as the SBI (Single Burning Item) test and costly large-scale experiments. By offering a practical balance, this approach enables focused investigation of component interactions and fire behaviour under controlled and realistic conditions. It allows for the identification of potential fire propagation mechanisms and system-level vulnerabilities without the need for full-scale validation, making it a valuable tool in the early stages of design and development. Testing results, in turn, support performance-based design by providing critical data for evaluating system behaviour under fire conditions, enabling innovation while ensuring safety through demonstrated performance.

The preliminary test with non-combustible material (see Supplementary Fig. S5) demonstrated that the heat flux reaching the

Fig. 14. Heat fluxes measured in Test 1 and Test 2, located in the upper edge of the test specimen and the sample with its outer face parallel to the vertical face of the test specimen.

façade in the 300 kW test more closely resembles typical values observed in real fires, approaching approximately 50 kW/m². The obtained results are comparable to those measured by Oleszkiewicz [53] in large-scale experiments. The latter used a fuel load of 25 kg/m², consisting of six wood cribs made of 41 mm × 89 mm pine sticks. When comparing the measured heat fluxes to the calibration criteria of NFPA 285, the values obtained at the lower and second radiometers (47 kW/m² and 38 kW/m², respectively) exceed the lower end of the NFPA 285 range. These measurements were taken at heights of 860 mm and 1459 mm above the top of the burner, respectively. According to NFPA 285, the required heat flux ranges during the final phase of the test (minutes 25–30) are 30–46 kW/m² at 610 mm and 27–41 kW/m² at 1219 mm above the lintel. Our results fall within or slightly exceed these ranges. It is also important to note that the 300 kW heat output was maintained throughout the entire test duration, in contrast to the NFPA 285 test, where the heat release rate increases over time. This constant heat input represents a conservative approach, strengthening the representativeness of our results for worst-case fire scenarios and providing a basis for scaling up to full-scale fire tests. In the newly developed European procedure for assessing façade fire performance, the medium exposure scenario also involves a maximum heat release rate of approximately 300 kW, though it follows a time-dependent curve rather than remaining constant, reflecting more realistic fire development.

Regarding the evaluation criteria, the inclusion of the criterion related to burning falling parts is relevant to fire safety in building materials, particularly in scenarios where flaming debris may contribute to fire spread. However, the regulatory adoption of the corresponding requirement remains uncertain. National authorities may adopt the criterion based on local risks and policy priorities, but its application remains highly variable across jurisdictions. Ongoing discussions within the European context, particularly within the upcoming harmonised fire performance assessment framework, indicate growing interest in establishing such criteria as key parameter.

Nevertheless, the developed intermediate-scale test procedure should be considered with caution, as validation has only been done in one type of multilayer façade systems. Main limitations are listed below.

- Burner position: placing the burner so that its external surface is aligned with the outer face of the sample could be considered, as has been proposed in the Draft International Standard ISO/DIS 13782-1 [65]. This could change the flame behaviour under the same combustion conditions, so this should be carefully analysed [67].
- Constant Heat source: the use of a fixed fire source intensity may inadequately represent the variability and dynamics of real fire scenarios, and defining a fire growth curve could be a good solution [61].
- Instrumentation constraints: The measurement system, including the relatively large number of thermocouples, may introduce complexity. Besides, radiative heat transfer on temperature measurements should be considered, in particular the external thermocouples located at 10 mm outwards from the external face of the cladding panel.
- Data acquisition: a shorter acquisition interval would improve the temporal resolution of the data, particularly for capturing rapid temperature changes during fire events. In this regard, ISO/DIS 13785-1:2025 defines a sampling period of 3 s [65], and the new European approach for façade fire performance specifies that data collection shall not exceed 5 s intervals [37].
- Repeatability: To improve the repeatability of the test, our procedure is conducted indoors to minimize the impact of external environmental variables. Additionally, a gas burner is used as the ignition source instead of a wood crib, providing a more consistent and controllable heat. Although wood cribs are widely used in large-scale fire tests, the possibility of using a propane gas is also being analysed for the future European façade method. This enables an increased reproducibility and possibilities to reduce total façade height [68]. However, it should be noted that the intermediate scale itself introduces inherent variability, particularly due to fluctuations in the airflow at the inlet, which can affect combustion conditions even under controlled indoor settings. Additionally, ISO 13785-1 does not specify a calibration procedure for the test, and while ISO/DIS 13785-1 includes Annex B as an informative annex, it notes that this annex will be finalized in a subsequent revision. For future testing, it is necessary to verify burner output and duct-flow conditions, as emphasized by Guillaume et al. [69].
- Detail representation: intermediate-scale tests necessarily simplify façade assemblies and do not reproduce all construction details, such as window openings, which can critically influence fire performance [70].
- Vertical sides of the specimen: open sides in intermediate-scale setups tend to reduce heat release rates due to a diminished chimney effect, which can influence test outcomes and fire dynamics [40]. In this regard, the last version of ISO/DIS 13785-1 proposed to seal the vertical sides. We recognize the importance of further studies exploring how sealing or opening specimen boundaries impacts fire behaviour and the validity of intermediate-scale tests.
- Vertical fire spread: A limitation of intermediate-scale setups is their reduced vertical extent, which limits their ability to simulate realistic multi-storey fire spread along façades. While they provide valuable insights into material flammability and component-level fire behaviour, full assessment of vertical propagation generally requires larger-scale testing. Intermediate-scale procedures may not fully capture all aspects of façade fire dynamics [40].

5.2. Discussion of the fire performance of the façade system

During the initial design phase of the test specimen, only a cavity barrier in the registrable area and the use of a steel lintel were considered as fire protection measures. However, based on the outcomes of the first test, a comprehensive redesign of the specimen was undertaken for the second test campaign. This redesign incorporated multiple passive fire protection (PFP) elements to mitigate fire propagation not only in the registrable area but also across other critical points identified in the first test. In addition, the outer layer configuration was intentionally modified with respect to Sample 1, leveraging the flexibility of the 2 MF façade system to explore diverse technological combinations and broaden the experimental scope, as detailed in Section 3.3.

The combination of the selected PFP elements, together with the position of horizontal joints, effectively delayed or prevented fire propagation through the cavities (see [Supplementary Figs. S1\(b\) and S2\(b\)](#)), while also reducing thermal degradation of the lower aluminium frame. Despite these improvements, the issue of flaming particle ejection could not be fully eliminated, though its occurrence was delayed. The redesign strategy focused on the following key aspects.

- Delaying flame propagation through the air cavity, panel joints, and registrable area by integrating cavity barriers and intumescent tapes.
- Preventing degradation of the aluminium frame due to elevated temperatures in the vertical registrable area, which could otherwise facilitate flame spread and compromise the structural integrity of the system. To address this, stone wool barriers were strategically overlaid on the aluminium profiles.

Although the contribution of each of the measure cannot be quantified, the second test successfully prevented vertical flame propagation, achieving flame burnout before the fire reached the upper part of the specimen. The increase in heat flux during Test 2 ([Fig. 14](#)) was anticipated, as the various passive protection measures implemented effectively limited the inlet of heat into the test specimen. This is supported by the differences between internal and external temperature measurements ([Figs. 11 and 12](#)), which indicate a significant thermal insulation effect. The sharp increase in heat flux at the end of Test 1 ([Fig. 14](#)) indicates accelerated thermal transfer to the exterior once the system's protective capacity was exceeded, meaning a loss of thermal integrity in the system.

Nevertheless, loud cracking noises were detected in Test 2. This may have been influenced by the installation of the fire protection measures, as they significantly reduced the temperature inside the cavity and resulted in a higher temperature gradient between the exterior and interior of the glass surfaces. An alternative explanation is that the panel configuration placed certain panels closer to the burner, resulting in more pronounced thermal gradients that could have induced cracking in the glass panels.

Although previous studies have shown that cracking can promote interlayer combustion [71], visual observations at the early-stage of the Test 2 did not reveal any ignition following the cracking. This suggests that the cracks were narrow, limiting the exposure of the interlayer to air and thereby preventing ignition. Furthermore, both visual inspection and temperature analysis do not indicate any degradation in performance. On the contrary, the panel in Test 1 appears to have suffered more extensive damage. In Test 2, the most affected area was the section directly exposed to the burner, whereas the portion extending beyond the burner remained in place. This suggests that, in this case, the cavity barrier played a more critical role in protecting the panel than the presence of cracks.

No measures could be implemented to prevent the fall of flaming droplets to the ground, which might result in a larger and more hazardous fire, as downward flame spread or ignition of secondary fires could happen [72]. This phenomenon occurred for several reasons. In the case of PV panels because the cracking of glass panes caused by thermal gradients and the combustion of the gasket sealant located between the aluminium frame and the various panels. One measure that could be investigated in this regard is to change the thicknesses of the interlayer or, in particular, the glass thickness, which plays a more significant role for breakage times than the interlayer thickness [71]. In the case of the tested HPL panels, these showed falling of flaming droplets due to its combustibility. Avoiding the installation of this type of modules above evacuation exits without adequate fire protection measurements might be a good solution to mitigate this hazard [73]. Another solution could be the use of flame retardant sealants [74].

A cost-benefit analysis should be considered to evaluate the effectiveness and proportionality of the implemented fire protection measures. While the redesign successfully mitigated flame spread and improved fire performance, it is possible that some of the measures may have been too conservative. Further investigation is needed to determine whether a more balanced approach could achieve similar safety outcomes with reduced complexity or cost.

The implementation of 2 MF systems in real buildings should incorporate the protection measures validated in Test 2, as these interventions have demonstrated their effectiveness in enhancing the fire performance of the system. Furthermore, future research in this field will be essential to verify additional design solutions and to expand the evidence base needed to support safe and robust integration of 2 MF systems.

6. Conclusion

This study presents a comprehensive methodology for assessing the fire performance of multilayer modular façades (2 MF), addressing a critical gap in early-stage design. The approach enables iterative fire safety evaluations during the design phase, shifting from reactive to preventive fire safety strategies. This represents a significant advancement in performance-based façade design.

1. Methodology and testing framework

The developed methodology is general and transferable to other façade systems. The intermediate-scale testing procedure and evaluation criteria are tailored to 2 MF systems, with specific thresholds derived from this case. While the framework is broadly applicable, thresholds may require adaptation for different materials, cavity geometries, or mounting concepts.

2. Fire-performance improvements

The study identifies key fire performance factors in 2 MF systems: cavity barriers, joints, material fire reaction, and system configuration. Design adaptations, such as passive fire protection, steel lintels, and protected transition elements, effectively mitigate flame spread and chimney effects. However, in the case study, the risk of falling burning debris has remained unresolved.

3. Testing and data insights

The novel intermediate-scale test simulates realistic fire conditions and provides detailed insights into fire propagation, temperature distribution, and heat flux. The data supports systematic design improvements and offers a robust framework for iterative development. Future work should explore dynamic heat sources, correlation with large-scale tests, and calorimetric measurements (e. g., HRR, THR) to enhance reproducibility and realism.

4. Implications and future research

The methodology offers more accurate fire performance insights than standard small-scale tests, due to the complexity of 2 MF systems. Intermediate-scale analysis is essential for reliable evaluation. Future research should assess the sustainability impact of fire resilience strategies and validate the framework across diverse façade systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Olaia Aurrekoetxea-Arratibel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Izaskun Alvarez-Alava:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Arritokieta Eizaguirre-Iribar:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **Xabier Olano-Azkune:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Peru Elguezabal:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobpe.2026.115831>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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